

THE CHALLENGES ASSOCIATED WITH IMPLEMENTING A NOVEL PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACH IN THE FIELD OF UZBEK LITERATURE

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Annotation This thesis is devoted to the issues of a new approach to psychological issues in the science of Uzbek literature.

Key words: Literature, mentality, approach, artistic work, high efficiency, style, skill, creator, artistic-aesthetic phenomenon, artistic work, artistic elements, improvement, genres, means of artistic representation

The first chapter of the work describes the theoretical issues of the topic. The chapter reflects the unique characteristics of psychological issues, as well as theoretical and scientific views on the subject. In the second chapter, the pedagogical foundations of teaching the subject, i.e., tasks related to the analysis of psychological issues during practical training on the subject, methodological support of practical training are given.

In the work of the graduation project, it is justified that a new approach to the issues of psychology in the science of literature is highly effective for the student studying the work of art. Through it, it was determined that students' knowledge and creativity can be developed

In fiction, psychological analysis is one of the main indicators of artistry, and it gives life to the work. The analysis of the mood determines the author's style, originality in the image and artistic skill. The perfection of literature, its greatness, is determined, first of all, by the extent to which the artistic-aesthetic phenomenon such as psychological analysis is discovered, by the extent to which the dialectics of the human soul and human heart are revealed.

We all know that in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which has chosen its own path of independent socio-economic development, the fundamental reform of the education system, raising it to the level of modern requirements, and raising a mature generation for the future has become a priority direction of state policy. I know.

The writer skillfully used the art of mental analysis in the novel. As he reveals the inner world of the heroes of the work through various poetic means, these artistic images are directed to reveal the idea of the work, develop the artistic logic in it, and increase the effectiveness of the work. In this regard, the writer skillfully uses the dream episode as a poetic tool of spiritual analysis. In the example of this work, the psychological portrait and internal monologue in the interpretation of Pirimkul Kadirov achieves artistic perfection by performing several poetic tasks at the same time. As the well-known literary critic Azod Sharafutdinov once said: "In order to educate the reader, literature should affect not only his mind and thoughts, but also his heart, pleasure, and feelings." Only such works have the right to be called true examples of art" {1}.

Several principles of education lead the organization of literature classes in order to form a student as a virtuous and spiritual person. In traditional education, it is the teacher's duty to ensure that lessons are relevant to life. In the lessons aimed at the spiritual maturity of the student, they themselves learn the concepts and laws of science based on life events, and return from theory to life. The teacher leads this process with guiding questions and tasks.

Students respect the scientific and life truths they have found. Theoretical concepts are clarified and deepened by understanding existing existence. Students learn to find the basis of various events that they may encounter in life by analyzing the personality of the literary characters and the events expressed in the work.

Full connection of education with life requires coherence between organizational aspects and methods of teaching. It is necessary not to introduce various artificial methods and methods into the practice of the educational system, but to achieve their connection with life and existing natural laws. Let the student apply the knowledge he has learned in the lesson in life or draw a scientific conclusion based on what he has seen in life. Only then, the knowledge imparted will be settled not only in the student's memory, but also in his thinking and spirit, becoming his property. A student who hears one thing in school and sees something else in life loses faith in the truths taught in lessons. The most correct way is education based on real life facts.

The main goal of national pedagogy in front of these academic subjects is to form good moral qualities in students. It is possible to cultivate beautiful qualities and positive qualities in the human personality by teaching the student to be influenced by the word, feel it and enjoy it with the help of artistic words in literature classes. It is understood through literature that the words and deeds of good-natured, healthy spiritual people are worthy of themselves, and the owner of a pure heart is always worthy of encouragement and blessings. These works are carried out directly by studying works of art and analyzing texts;

In order to ensure the spiritual maturity of the reader, in the process of analyzing the work of art, they are encouraged to express their opinion in the discussion about the events, personality, actions, sufferings and joys of the characters reflected in the text, to support or condemn a point of view or activity. This work is carried out with the help of questions and assignments presented on the text of the work, with the help of problem situations. While answering the questions, the student refers to the text of the work, searches, listens to his friends, expresses his views, compares them with others', controls, and draws conclusions. In the course of this activity, the student works on the formation of his spirituality and self-education.

Literature is a treasure of manners, and by ensuring the student's access to this treasure of his own free will, it will be possible to implement self-education while working on works and expressing reactions in literature classes;

The reader must discover for himself the artistic and life truths that were instilled in the work of art by its author, advanced by the creators of the textbook. The reader should be given the opportunity to discover the spiritual qualities of the heroes of the work with the help of questions and assignments based on the text. Discovery is always fun, and students should be given the opportunity to experience this fun. The taste of discovery encourages the reader to delve deeper into the essence of the work and make new discoveries. A person wants to do the work that gave him peace over and over again, to deepen it and feel that presence again. Synchronization of literature lessons with such natural qualities characteristic of a person brings up a healthy spirituality in the student's personality;

In literature classes, the teacher should be a partner, not a governor. Learning and education is carried out by the student himself in cooperation between the teacher and the student. The

main tasks of the teacher in the lesson are to read the work expressively and effectively and to ask the tasks given in the textbook regarding the text of the work...

It is known that every work is the product of one person's creativity. He even created a sample of folklore. In that work, a person pours out his pain, puts his dreams, painful or happy moments of his life in it. Feeling the spirit of the creator of the work, feeling his joys and sorrows is important for spiritual purification. Evaluating the experiences and personalities of the heroes of the work while working on the text allows the reader to learn about a person and form his identity through acquaintance. One of the important aspects of today's literary education is to understand the writer who made the reader share his joys, sorrows and sufferings, who made him sympathize with his indifference, and to know his personality by studying his writings. Evaluating the heroes of the work forms students' ability to evaluate the people around them based on their actions;

One of the important directions in education is a creative approach to it. A creative approach to teaching is becoming a priority in teaching everything from science and technology to philosophy, the arts, the natural sciences, and the humanities around the world. The creative thinking of the individual, which is the basis of the creative approach in education, is a higher concept than the ability to give random ideas. It is a real skill based on knowledge and experience that allows a person to achieve better results in difficult situations. Creative thinking is among the skills of independent and logical thinking in educational practice. Societies and organizations all over the world increasingly feel the need for innovative knowledge and creativity in solving problems, especially in the education system, and this, in turn, makes this field more innovative and creative.

The concepts of "creative" and "creativity" (translated from Latin and English, "create" means creation, "creative" means creator) - the ability of creativity, which describes the ability of an individual to create new ideas and is part of talent as an independent factor. , is estimated as

First of all, the pedagogue working in the educational system should have the qualities of creativity. This creates the basis for the qualitative and effective organization of his personal abilities and professional activities. Organization of didactic support of teaching based on a creative approach guarantees the effectiveness of the teaching process.

Teacher's creativity in the educational process:

- creating creative questions and assignments that increase students' interest in reading;
- be able to create educational problems based on various pictures, images, tables, diagrams, multimedia materials, electronic literature, Internet materials, electronic dictionaries, work in small groups, and guide students to the solution by making them interested in them;
- to be able to distinguish creative, independent and logical thinking skills and independent activities characteristic of students;
- such skills of students are reflected in the types of work, such as the ability to distinguish the level of education and adequately evaluate it.

The ability of the teacher to achieve independent, logical and creative thinking of his students, to motivate and encourage such activities in the educational process is the basis for encouraging others in the class to engage in such creative activities.

A creative approach to education is the basis of significant innovations for the whole society as a basis for directing students to creative thinking. At the same time, it is also a universal and equalizing phenomenon. That is, any person, to one degree or another, has the ability to

think creatively, independently and logically. According to experts in the field of education and psychologists, the thinking process related to creative activity has a positive effect on the development of a number of other personal skills. That is, metacognitive (thinking about thinking, knowing about knowledge, the ability to understand the mind) ability is the basis for the formation of interpersonal skills, self-awareness and problem-solving skills. In addition, a creative approach to education is important for personal development, educational success, and future professional and life success.

Based on a creative approach to education, it is possible to develop an individual to the level of the requirements of the international research program aimed at evaluating his creative thinking, and to achieve positive changes in educational policy and pedagogy. Today, the PIRLS and PISA studies also provide clear, reliable, and actionable assessment tools that help administrators make evidence-based decisions about student creative thinking and performance. The results achieved in this regard in the developed countries of the world are the cause of debates about the importance and methods of developing this important skill through education in the students of national education.

The main task of a creative approach to education is to enable the student to live a successful life in society, to form and develop the skills and abilities needed today and in the future. Creative thinking and creative activity, which is the basis of this approach, are important skills that today's youth should have. These skills will help them adapt to a world that is constantly and rapidly changing, requiring individuals with "21st century skills" beyond basic literacy.

Creative thinking and active thinking, which is the basis of the process of creative approach to education, is globally recognized as "providing new ideas and solutions". A creative approach to education:

- 1) describe knowledge, observe and feel the situation, sympathize with others;
- 2) search for ideas, development and research of new ideas;
- 3) to discover the relevance of knowledge, to present one's point of view in different fields;
- 4) "play" with unusual or powerful ideas;
- 5) imagine, express, develop, create a new product;
- 6) refers to activities such as recognizing the novelty of the solution and finding new solutions.

The importance of developing creative thinking and activity at school is not limited only to the labor market. School plays an important role in discovering creative talents for young people.

Also, in the creative direction of education, the creative activity of students is supported by interpreting their learning events, experiences and behaviors in a new and personally meaningful way. The student's imagination and curiosity come into play in the process of creative education, creative thinking thus becomes a means of mutual agreement. In order to increase the student's motivation (inner need) and interest in the school, it is necessary to establish new forms of education that take into account the creative potential and enthusiasm of all students. It can also help students who are not very interested in reading, and it can serve to express their opinion and reveal their potential.

In a creative approach to education, creative thinking and activity, like a number of other skills, are developed through a practical, goal-oriented approach. It may seem to some teachers that the development of the student's creative thinking and creative activity is at the

expense of other subjects in the curriculum. In fact, students tend to think and act creatively in all classes.

Creative (creative) thinking and activity are developed through approaches that support research and creativity instead of blind memorization and repetition during each lesson aimed at mastering knowledge. Teachers should be able to distinguish creative activities, create conditions suitable for such attitudes, and be inclined to creativity, like their students, and know how to help creative approach to any work. The teacher should have a clear idea of how creativity (creative thinking, creative activity) occurs in the educational process, understand that certain time and conditions are required for creative ideas to arise in the educational process, and be able to achieve this in practice. necessary.

A creative approach to education directs students to acquire the ability to effectively participate in the creation, evaluation and implementation of ideas that bring original and effective solutions, achievements and imagination to impressive manifestations in any field.

Another approach that is leading in the educational directions of developed countries is called the cognitive approach. The basis of the concept of "cognitive" is derived from the Latin word "sognitio", which means to know and understand. The English word "cognitive" means "learned", which means that a person develops skills and abilities to acquire knowledge by working hard and mentally and spiritually. Today, in the practice of national educational science, the concepts that have been used in the Uzbek language for a thousand years have been brought into the practice of national education in the form of English terms (creative, cognitive). This is a proof of the distance of the employees of the official organizations from the field, lack of knowledge of educational practice, national methodology science. Whether these terms are still considered "innovation" (like scratching the right ear with the left hand), it will be necessary to talk about their interpretation [1.].

There are a number of terms associated with this term, such as cognitive grammar, cognitive linguistics, cognitive psychology, cognitive education, and cognitive orientation. The term "cognitive" is understood in connection with processes such as knowledge of objective reality (the world), its perception by a person, memory, explanation and processing of information. As a result of independent reading and learning, the student finds the necessary knowledge, absorbs it to the maximum extent, and this is a cognitive (knowledge, mastery) approach to education. In the language of experts, the "cognitive approach" can be understood as a cognitive process in speech activity. The cognitive process ends with the acquisition of knowledge.

The purpose of the article is to study ways of effectively using the analysis of a new approach to psychological issues in Uzbek literature classes.

Through the article, we tried to find solutions to the following tasks and problems:

researching issues such as the use of analysis of new approaches to psychological issues in Uzbek literature classes;

Today's educational process refers to the "cognitive approach" to teaching, which means that the student acquires knowledge through the activity of searching for knowledge not only from the textbook or the information provided by the teacher, but also from additional literature, and gaining a certain understanding with the help of guiding questions. is implied. In this process, the questions and tasks created by the teacher based on the content of the subject, first of all, should be interesting for the student, and at the same time, they should be in a way

that ensures the conscious mastering of the subject and directs him to independent research in this regard. It is the basis of cognitive education.

Instead of the teacher trying to store knowledge in the memory of the students using various methods and methods effectively, and the students simply memorizing or memorizing and repeating the given information, they are independent according to the directions of the teacher. The knowledge that he has learned will take place in his psyche, where it will be preserved for life.

In the next period, the terms "cognitive education" and "cognitive approach" are entering the practice of education of all academic subjects in national educational science. This kind of education or cognitive approach to education, unlike reproductive education, encourages independent learning, teaches ways of learning on the basis of inquiry, recommends methods, directs the student to independent acquisition of knowledge.

The main goal of cognitive education as one of the directions of psychology and pedagogy is to develop intellectual abilities of an individual. It promotes teaching based on a set of educational strategies aimed at increasing the student's ability to adapt to the acquisition of new knowledge.

Therefore, the principles and approaches of education, in particular, the principles of teaching literature and, in this case, directing students to creativity in all aspects, encouraging them to learn and acquire knowledge independently, are the guarantee of the development of the nation and the country.

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13. studying the importance and possibilities of a new approach to psychological issues in Uzbek literature classes;

14. creation of methodological support from the analysis of a new approach to psychological issues in Uzbek literature classes (syllabus, technological map, practical training materials);
15. Academician Izzat Sultan says about the image of a person in literature: "A person is the subject of an image in literature. There is no fiction where there is no image of a person, and at the same time, "image of a person" means the image of a person's inner world, his experiences." We can see the practical expression of these theoretical information in an artistic work in the novel "Khumayun and Akbar" by Pirimkul Kadyrov.

